

ACT4CAP27

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Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027

This is the 2nd newsletter of the ACT4CAP27 project WHERE YOU CAN:

- Find out what ACT4CAP27 is all about
- Read about the latest developments of the project
- Know more about networking with other EU projects
- Get information on upcoming events

What is ACT4CAP27 ?

ACT4CAP27 is an EC funded 5-year Horizon Europe research and innovation action, aiming to enhance analytical capabilities, tools, and collaborative technical infrastructure within the policy modelling community, to provide support for evidence-based EU agri-food policies post-2027.

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[Read our project flyer in 8 languages on Zenodo](#)

Dear ACT4CAP27 Community,

As we reach the midpoint of 2025, it's a fitting moment to reflect on the progress ACT4CAP27 has made in shaping the future of EU agricultural policy through science, collaboration, and stakeholder engagement.

Our **Annual Meeting in Rome** set the tone for a productive year, bringing together partners to align our vision and activities. Since then, we've made steady progress: from finalizing the **Fast Track Scenario narratives** in WP6, to advancing our conceptual frameworks, data platforms, and model integration. The series of monthly held **WP Leads meetings** confirm strong cross-WP coordination.

A key milestone was our **Stakeholder Consultation on 6 May**, which gathered over 60 participants and confirmed just how essential stakeholder input is to shape our work. Feedback emphasized the need for deeper dialogue and even greater inclusivity — insights we will carry into the **autumn follow-up meeting**. Our **Scientific and Policy Advisory Board (SPAB)** has also been a valuable sounding board, ensuring our work remains policy-relevant and scientifically grounded.

ACT4CAP27's presence at events such as the **EU Vision Conference** and **SIEPI Workshop** has strengthened our links with the policy and academic communities. Our Ukrainian partners have also raised ACT4CAP27's profile through active participation in national events, underlining the project's broad relevance.

Capacity building is central to our impact. We've launched the **CAPRI and AGMEMOD trainings**, opened the **AMYRN Young Researcher Network** fund to support early-career exchanges — laying the groundwork for a robust community of agri-food policy modellers.

Through collaboration with Horizon Europe peers like **BrightSpace**, **LAMASUS** and **Tools4CAP**, we are jointly advancing state-of-the-art tools for sustainable policy design. We also celebrated the publication of our first **open-access article** and welcomed followers via our new **Bluesky channel**.

As we look ahead, key priorities include our **next policy brief**, preparations for the **interim technical report**, and participations for the modelling projects' cluster EC event in September. Planning is also underway for our next in-person stakeholder meeting in autumn.

On a somber note, we take a moment to remember our dear colleague **Professor Luca Salvatici**, whose sudden passing earlier this year deeply affected us all. His legacy as a scholar, mentor, and collaborator continues to inspire our work.

As you read this newsletter, I invite you to discover how our shared efforts are building knowledge and tools for the future CAP. Your support has been and is remaining vital — and we look forward to the road ahead.

Thank you for being an integral part of the ACT4CAP27 community.
Best regards,

Siemen van Berkum

ACT4CAP27 Project Coordinator, on behalf of the ACT4CAP27 team

Latest news from ACT4CAP27

ACT4CAP27 Stakeholder Consultation on the Future of the CAP | 6 May 2025

Organized by ECORYS on 6 May 2025, the ACT4CAP27 project held an online stakeholder consultation, bringing together researchers, policymakers, and representatives from agri-food associations across Europe.

[Read more »](#)

In memoriam Professor Luca Salvatici

It is with deep sadness that the ACT4CAP27 consortium acknowledges the passing of Professor Luca Salvatici, a distinguished economist and esteemed colleague from Roma Tre University.

[Read more »](#)

Meet the Scientific & Policy Advisory Board of ACT4CAP27

ACT4CAP27 is proud to be supported by a distinguished Scientific and Policy Advisory Board (SPAB), composed of internationally recognised scientists and policy experts who bring a wealth of knowledge, experience, and independent perspective to the project.

[Read more »](#)

ACT4CAP27 Annual Meeting 2025

The ACT4CAP27 Annual Consortium Meeting 2025 took place at the University of Roma Tre, bringing together project partners to review progress and plan the next steps in supporting EU agri-food policies beyond 2027.

[Read summary Day 1 »](#)

[Read summary Day 2 »](#)

[Read press release»](#)

Further project Activities

WP8 WP leaders meeting 20 May 2025

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WP8 workpackage leaders' meeting 20 May 2025, online

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WP6 meeting on fast track scenarios 12 May 2025

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WP6 meeting on fast track scenarios, 12 May 2025, online

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ACT4CAP27 #RESULTS

NEW OPEN ACCESS ARTICLE

Predicting policy funding allocation with Machine Learning

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Open access Article from ACT4CAP27 in Socio-Economic Planning Sciences

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ACT4CAP27 is now on Bluesky: @act4cap27.eu

2025: new COM channel

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ACT4CAP27 is now also on Bluesky!

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ACT4CAP27 Highlights from Ukraine

ACT4CAP27 Presented at Zhytomyr Dialogue Event 24 April 2025

Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027

Розвиток потенціалу та аналітичних інструментів для підтримки спільної аграрної політики після 2027 року

Николай Ольга, Поліський національний університет

24 квітня 2025 | Житомир, Україна

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Strengthening Regional Cooperation: ACT4CAP27 presented at Zhytomyr Dialogue Event

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ACT4CAP27 presented at "GREEN & DIGITAL POLISSIA: AGRICULTURE" Forum 16 January 2025

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ACT4CAP27 Project Spotligted at "Green & Digital Polissia: Agriculture" Forum

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Capacity building & AMYRN news

WE COOPERATE IN CAPACITY BUILDING

ACT4CAP27 BRIGHT SPACE TOOLS₄CAP

17-20 June 2025
THE HAGUE, THE NETHERLANDS

AGMEMOD
AGRI-FOOD PROJECTIONS
Training 2025

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AGMEMOD Training Course, 17-20 June 2025, The Hague, NL

The Course is designed to support new modellers in becoming familiar with AGMEMOD, a key tool for agricultural economic analysis. The training will also foster collaboration and knowledge exchange among AGMEMOD consortium members and broader research communities.

[Read more »](#)

ACT4CAP27 CAPACITY BUILDING

ACT4CAP27
Agri-Food Model
Young Researcher
Network
(AMYRN)

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ACT4CAP27 Agricultural Model Young Researcher Network (AMYRN)

As part of ACT4CAP27, the Agri-Food Model Young Researcher Network (AMYRN) aims to support building a network of young researchers – within the ACT4CAP27 partner organisations – that have an interest in using simulation modelling approaches to inform agri-food policies.

[Read more »](#)

WP5 Task 5.4 Planning Training Activities

ACT4CAP27 CAPACITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES

On-line meeting
4 April 2025

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Task 5.4 Meeting – Planning Training Activities for 2025

On 4 April 2025, an online meeting was held to discuss Task 5.4 – Planning Training Activities for 2025 as part of ACT4CAP27’s capacity-building efforts. The session, convened by WP5 leader Maria Blanco (UPM), focused on key aspects of upcoming training initiatives.

[Read more »](#)

BRIGHT SPACE WE COOPERATE ACT4CAP27

Capacity Building:
CAPRI Developer Seminar
11-12 March 2025
Berlin, Germany

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CAPRI Developer Seminar, 11-12/03/2025, Berlin, DE

The Seminar 2025 took place on 11-12 March 2025 in Berlin, Germany, bringing together researchers, software developers, and agricultural economists to discuss advancements in CAPRI, a leading simulation model for economic analysis in agriculture.

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ACT4CAP27 Communication Events

ACT4CAP27 at the EU Vision Conference on Agriculture & Food, 8/05/2025, Brussels, BE

At the 2025 EU Vision Conference on Agriculture and Food ACT4CAP27 and its fellow project BrightSpace both joined the debate on shaping a vibrant, resilient agri-food sector.

[Read more »](#)

ACT4CAP27 at XXIII SIEPI Workshop 31 January 2025, Bologna, IT

ACT4CAP27 work presented at XXIII SIEPI Workshop, 31/01/2025, Bologna, IT

Cristina Vaquero-Piñeiro, representing the UNIROMA3 team within the ACT4CAP27 project, showcased their research on predicting EU funding success using machine learning at the XXIII Annual Workshop of the Società Italiana di Economia e Politica Industriale (SIEPI).

[Read more »](#)

Upcoming events

- ➔ [AGMEMOD Training Course, 17-20 June, 2025, The Hague, NL](#)
- ➔ [IAMO Forum 2025, 18-20 June 2025, Halle, DE](#)
- ➔ [14th AIEAA Conference, Reconciling competitiveness and sustainability in the agrifood system: the role of knowledge and innovation, 18-20 June 2025, Pisa, IT](#)
- ➔ [Summer school: Risk Analysis, Risk Management, and Resilience in Agriculture, 23-27 June 2025, Wageningen, NL](#)
- ➔ [ESA's Living Planet Symposium 2025, 23–27 June 2025 Vienna, AT](#)
- ➔ [OECD Green Growth & Sustainable Development Forum 2025 | 2–3 July 2025 | Paris, FR & Online](#)
- ➔ [7th Edition of the International School for Advanced Training: Impact Evaluation of Development Policies: Concepts, Methods, Applications, 23/06-04/07 2025, online](#)
- ➔ [Executive Course on the Vision for Agriculture and Food, 25-27 June 2025, online](#)
- ➔ [2025 EAAE Congress, 26-29 August 2025, Bonn, DE](#)
- ➔ [XV Congress of Agri-food Economics of the Spanish AEEA, 3-5 September, Granada, ES](#)
- ➔ [XXI European Rural Development Network Conference “Food systems transition for sustainable rural development”, 23-25 September 2025, Bucharest, RO](#)

Networking and Cooperation with Horizon Europe Projects

ACT4CAP27 & BrightSpace Collaborate: CAPRI Course 2025, 17/04-17/07, hybrid
[Read more »](#)

Driving EU Agricultural Policy Forward: ACT4CAP27, BrightSpace, & LAMASUS Collaborate
[Read more »](#)

Further highlights from our fellow projects

- 2nd Modelling Workshop to Advance SJOS Indicator Integration [Read more »](#)
- Expert Consultation: Animal Welfare in a Safe & Just Operating Space [Read more »](#)
- BrightSpace results on Zenodo [Read more »](#)
- BrightSpace Agricultural SJOS Platform [Read more »](#)

- Tools4CAP at the EU CAP Network's Good Practice Workshop, 3-4 April, Bari, IT [Read more »](#)
- Inventory of methods & tools for the design, implementation and monitoring of CAP Strategic Plans [Read more »](#)
- TOOLS4CAP results [Read more »](#)
- TOOLS4CAP Academy [Read more »](#)

Join us and be part of the ACT4CAP27 Stakeholder Community!

The **ACT4CAP27 Stakeholder Community** offers a unique platform for networking and exchanging knowledge and experience related to the future of EU agri-food policies. All interest groups who have a stake in EU agriculture - including farmers, consumers, civil society organisations, agri-businesses and policy governance representatives across the different member states - are welcome to join our stakeholder community and contribute with new perspectives.

Reach out to us:
<https://act4cap27.eu/stakeholder-platform/>

ACT4CAP27

More information will be sent in our next ACT4CAP27 newsletter scheduled for winter 2025.

Thank you for signing up to the ACT4CAP27 newsletters.

Further information can be found on the ACT4CAP27 project homepage:

<https://act4cap27.eu/>

FOLLOW US ON OUR CHANNELS

PARTNERS

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